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State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article provides information about the history and development of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, its conditions, educational directions, scientists who worked in the conservatory, the meaning and origin of the word conservatory.

Key words: conservatory, Tashkent, center of knowledge, Central Asia, music, theater, classic, State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, scientists.

Uzbekistan Conservatory is the state institution of higher music education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the oldest conservatory in Central Asia. Located in Tashkent. The conservatory is the leading educational institution in the field of musical art in the republic.

Tashkent State Conservatory was established in 1936 on the basis of the Higher School of Music, opened in 1934. Viktor Zuckerman, Lev Danilevich, Yuriy Fortunatov were among the famous teachers sent to Uzbekistan from the Moscow Conservatory in the early years. The second wave of Russian musicians came to Tashkent during the evacuation during the Great Patriotic War. This contributed to the establishment of the university and the development of music science in Uzbekistan. For a long time, the conservatory was the only such institution in Central Asia, which has been training highly qualified specialists for music institutions throughout the region. Graduates of the conservatory worked in the leading musical theaters of the neighboring Soviet republics - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan.

One of the activities of the conservatory was the study of the musical heritage of Uzbekistan. Departments of the history and theory of national traditional music, and since 1972 a special department of Eastern music has been established. Since 1939, the Central Music Boarding School named after V. A. Uspensky, now transformed into an academic lyceum for gifted children. In 1976, the conservatory was named after Mukhtar Ashrafi, who was the rector of the conservatory in 1971-

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An important stage of the educational process at the Uzbek conservatory is creative activity. The team of the conservatory holds more than 300 different concerts a year. 38 People's Artists of Uzbekistan, Honored Artist of Uzbekistan and other specialists with honorary titles, as well as more than 80 laureates of international and republican competitions will contribute to the performance of the concert. The scientific and methodological activity of the conservatory is mainly related to Uzbek classical and modern music, music creation of Central Asian and world nations, music theory and history, performance issues.

The new building built in 2002 on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov (chief architect V. Spivak, architects A. Kalislomov, R. Shokirov and others, artists O. Khabibulin, V. Gan, R. Khudoyberganov and others) has the most modern equipment and provided with instruments. The total area is 35,180 sq.m., it includes 305 auditoriums, 4 concert halls, 4 recording studios, sports halls, etc.

Until 1939, the Tashkent Conservatory occupied the former building of the Higher School of Music, and later moved to the building of the ballet school built according to the project of architects V. Brilevich, N. Goloshanov and A. Sidorov. It was created in the style of "Stalin's Empire". In the 90s of the last century, by the order of the

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President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, the construction of a new building in the national style began on Batir Zakirov street. The old building was transferred to Hamza Music College and demolished in 2010.

The State Conservatory of Uzbekistan includes six faculties:

- composition, musicology and piano;
- orchestral instruments;
- Eastern music;
- academic singing and choir conducting;
- pop art;
- training.

In 2020, Kamoliddin Orinboyev was appointed as the rector of the conservatory.

At the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, the scientific-methodical magazine "MUSIC" is published 4 times a year, and the online version of the Eurasian music science magazine is published 2 times a year.

Conservatory (ital. conservatorio - shelter) is a special music school. It provides education in various fields of music performance, composition and musicology in a specific system. Originally, an asylum for orphans and neglected children in Italy was called K. (the first was in Naples, 1537), where music (mainly singing) was taught as well as various crafts. From the end of the 17th century, the Italian conservatories became institutions that trained professional musicians. As a modern educational institution, K.s began to be outsourced in Europe from the end of the 18th century (Royal High School of Music in Stockholm, 1771; Music and Declamation K.si in Paris, 1795, etc.). Some foreign higher educational institutions of music are also called academy, high school, institute (for example, the Academy of Fine Arts in Baghdad, the Institute of Arabic Music in Cairo, etc.). In most European and American universities, only performers (musicians, singers, conductors) and composers are educated. Musicologists are trained in music faculties of universities. In Uzbekistan, Turkestan People's College (1918), Higher Music School since 1934, Tashkent College since 1936, and Uzbekistan Conservatory since 2002 have been operating in Uzbekistan. Mazkur K. has made a significant contribution to the

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development of national art as the main center for training highly qualified specialists in the fields of music performance, composition and musicology.

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